

ENVIRONMENTAL DIPLOMACY IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Introduction. Environmental diplomacy in Central Asia is becoming a crucial aspect of international cooperation in the face of increasing environmental issues and tensions related to water resource management. The Central Asian region faces unique challenges, including transboundary water resources of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers, which are vital for the economies of the upstream countries (Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan) and downstream countries (Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan). Amid water scarcity and growing political tensions, environmental diplomacy has emerged as a tool for maintaining stability and promoting sustainable development in the region.

Research Objective. The objective of this research is to identify mechanisms and patterns influencing environmental diplomacy in Central Asia, with a focus on water resources. The study aims to identify factors shaping the environmental policies of the region's countries and to analyze the effectiveness of existing agreements and coordinating bodies in ensuring sustainable water resource management.

Materials and Methods. The empirical basis of the research includes an analysis of international agreements, such as the Almaty Agreement, which regulate the joint use of transboundary water resources. Additionally, data on environmental and water initiatives were reviewed. The methodological approach involves a comparative analysis of the environmental policies and diplomacy of the region's countries, taking into account their economic interests.

Results. The results of the research indicate that environmental diplomacy in Central Asia is primarily focused on water resource management. Existing agreements provide a foundation for cooperation, but in practice, face challenges due to conflicting economic interests of the upstream and downstream countries. Downstream countries seek increased water volumes for agricultural needs, while upstream countries require water resources for energy generation. The introduction of new coordination mechanisms and joint projects, such as the construction of hydropower plants, helps to reduce tensions and enhance the region's resilience.

Conclusions. Environmental diplomacy in Central Asia is an important tool for resolving conflicts related to water resources and contributes to strengthening regional stability. However, further development requires enhanced mechanisms of multilateral cooperation

and more flexible adaptation of international agreements to the economic interests and environmental needs of the region's countries.